

Chemical characterization of *Dichrostachys cinerea* extracts using GC-MS and column chromatography

Olawale A. Akinmusire¹, Ayodeji A. Dahunsi^{2#}

¹Department of Public Health, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Abuja, PMB 117, Garki Abuja, Nigeria

²Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Science, University of Abuja, PMB 117, Garki Abuja, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: *Dichrostachys cinerea*, a plant known for its extensive use in traditional medicine.

OBJECTIVE: *D. cinerea* was analyzed to identify its bioactive compounds and to assess its therapeutic potential.

METHODS: Using gas chromatography – mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and column chromatography, we identified and characterized the chemical constituents of *D. cinerea*, shedding light on their potential health benefits. The separation and purification of a variety of compounds were performed by column chromatography, while GC-MS allowed for detailed structural analysis of these bioactive components.

RESULTS: Our findings mark significant progress in the study of the chemical composition of *D. cinerea*, emphasizing its potential applications in pharmaceutical and medicinal fields. The identified compounds possessed useful pharmacological properties, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial activities. Obtained data significantly advances our understanding of the plant's bioactive properties and provides a foundation for future studies exploring its therapeutic potential.

CONCLUSION: The outcomes of this study have implications for the development of novel drugs and herbal remedies, underscoring the importance of *D. cinerea* as a valuable resource in the quest for new medicines.

Keywords: *Dichrostachys cinerea*, gas chromatography – mass spectrometry, column chromatography, antimicrobial, pharmaceutical, traditional medicine, biological activities, antioxidant

For correspondence: Ayodeji Adams Dahunsi, B.Sc., M.Sc., Assistant Lecturer/Ph.D. student, Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Science, University of Abuja, PMB 117, Garki Abuja, Nigeria., dahunsi.ayodeji@uniabuja.edu.ng

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INTRODUCTION

Plants synthesize a broad spectrum of bioactive compounds and serve as primary sources of many useful pharmaceuticals [1, 2, 3]. Traditional systems of medicine remain the main source of healthcare for over two-thirds of the world's population. Significant progress has been made in integrating traditional medicine with Western medicine in several developing countries, including China, India, and various nations across Africa. This integration, supported by advancements in modern

science and technology, has contributed to the promotion and development of traditional medicine [1, 2].

Plants have served as a vital source of medicine since the dawn of human civilization. Despite the significant advancements in allopathic medicine during the 20th century, plants remain a major source of therapeutic agents in both modern and traditional medical practices worldwide [1, 2]. It is estimated that approximately one-quarter of all pharmaceuticals used globally are

derived from plants [3], while many others are synthetic compounds obtained from natural precursors.

In recent years, there has been a growing preference for natural products [1, 2, 4]. Medicinal plants are highly valued for their bioactive compounds and unique chemical profiles, driving increased demand for plant-based medicines, healthcare products, pharmaceuticals, dietary supplements, and cosmetics.

Dichrostachys cinerea (Mimosae) is a medium-sized tree commonly found in the forests of Africa, Australia, India, and parts of Southeast Asia. It is known by various names, including “Sickle pod” and “acacia saint Domingue” in English, “Vada” in Karnataka, South India, “Kora” in Yoruba, and “Dundu” in Hausa, Nigeria [5, 6].

The leaves, bark, roots, and new shoots of *D. cinerea* have been widely used in traditional medicine to treat numerous ailments and diseases, ranging from fever to toothache [7, 8, 9]. This extensive usage highlights that *D. cinerea* is one of the most valuable plants used in traditional medicine. We hypothesized that phytochemical screening of *D. cinerea* extracts will reveal a range of compounds with diverse biological activities, including flavonoids, terpenoids, and phenolic acids.

Objectives:

1. To identify and characterize the bioactive compounds present in *D. cinerea* extracts using column chromatography and gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS).
2. To determine the chemical composition of *D. cinerea* extracts and assess their potential biological activities.
3. To evaluate the potential of *D. cinerea* extract as a source of novel bioactive compounds for pharmaceutical and medicinal applications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

This research was conducted in the microbiology laboratory at the University of Abuja main campus, Gwagwalada, Abuja, in the North-Central zone of Nigeria, in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT).

Collection and identification of plant materials

Fresh stem bark of *D. cinerea* was collected in September 2013 from plants growing in the Bwari Area Council, Abuja, Nigeria. The plant was identified and authenticated by a qualified botanist at the Department of Biological Sciences, Faculty of Science, University of Abuja.

Preparation and sterilization of culture media

All media used in this study were prepared in dehydrated form according to the manufacturer’s specifications and standard microbiological techniques. The culture media used included nutrient agar (TM MEDIA, India), nutrient broth (TM MEDIA, India), eosin methylene blue agar (HI MEDIA, India), mannitol salt agar (HI MEDIA, India), and Mueller-Hinton agar (TM MEDIA, India). Each medium was prepared by weighing the required quantities, adding deionized water to a conical flask, and shaking the flask until a clear solution was obtained. Sterilization was performed by autoclaving at 121°C and 15 psi for 15 min. After cooling to 45°C, the agar was dispensed into plates, test tubes, or Bijoux bottles, as appropriate.

Preparation of plant material

Fresh stem bark was air-dried to a constant weight and ground using a clean wooden mortar and pestle. The resulting powder was pulverized in a clean blender and stored in airtight containers until further analysis.

Extraction procedure

Powdered plant samples (200 g) were soaked in 2000 ml of methanol, ethanol, or distilled water for 72 h. The mixtures were shaken every 6 h to enhance solvent penetration. After 72 h, each mixture was filtered through a Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The filtrates (methanolic, ethanolic, and aqueous) were concentrated to 10 ml volume in a water bath and stored in Bijoux bottles for further analysis.

Phytochemical screening

The three crude extracts of *D. cinerea* were screened for phytochemicals using standard procedures to test for the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, saponins, tannins, terpenoids, sterols, phlobatannins, anthraquinones, balsams, and reducing sugars as outlined in the [10].

Test for alkaloids

A mixture of iodine in potassium iodide was added to 5 ml of the extract and shaken vigorously. A deep brown coloration indicates the presence of alkaloids [11].

Test for flavonoids

Zinc chips were added to 5 ml of the extract, followed by gradual addition of concentrated H₂SO₄. The reddish coloration indicates the presence of flavonoids [11].

Test for glycosides

H₂SO₄ (2.5 ml) was added to 5 ml of the extract and the mixture was boiled for 15 min and then allowed to cool. The solution was neutralized with 19% NaOH, followed by addition of Fehling solutions A and B. A brick-red precipitate of reducing sugars confirmed the presence of glycosides [11].

Test for saponins

To a test tube containing 5 ml of diluted extract, 10 ml of water was added and shaken vigorously for 2 min. The formation of froth, followed by an emulsion upon adding olive oil, indicated the presence of saponins [11].

Test for tannins

A 0.5 g sample of the aqueous, methanolic or ethanolic extract (0.5 ml of the aqueous extract, 0.64 ml of methanolic extract or 0.63 ml of ethanolic extract) was heated in 50 ml of distilled water for 3 min and filtered. A few drops of a 10% FeCl₃ solution were added to the filtrate. The blue color of the solution indicates the presence of tannins [11].

Test for balsams

Three drops of alcoholic ferric chloride were added to 4 ml of the extract, which was then warmed. The dark green color indicates the presence of balsams [11].

Test for reducing sugar content

Approximately 0.5 ml of each Fehling's solution A and B were added to a test tube. Then 0.5 ml of the extract was added, and the mixture was heated in a water bath. A brick-red precipitate indicated the presence of reducing sugars [11].

Test for terpenoids:

To the extract (0.5 g), 2 ml of chloroform were added, followed by the careful addition of 3 ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ to form a layer. The reddish-brown coloration at the interface indicated the presence of terpenoids [11].

Test for sterols:

One milliliter of the extract was mixed with 1 ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ in a test tube. The red coloration indicates the presence of sterols [11].

Test for phlobatannins

One milliliter of ferric chloride solution was added to 1 ml of the plant extract. A greenish-black or blue-black color indicates the presence of phlobatannins [12].

Test for anthraquinones

One milliliter of Shinoda reagent was added to 1 ml of plant extract. A reddish-brown or brownish-red color indicates the presence of anthraquinones [13].

Preparation of extracts solutions

Stock solutions of *D. cinerea* stem bark extracts (aqueous, methanolic, and ethanolic) were prepared following the method described in [14]. One gram of each dried extract residue was weighed using an analytical balance and dissolved in 1 ml of DMSO to prepare a 1000 mg/ml stock solution. The stock solution was used to prepare extract solutions with four different concentrations: 500, 250, 125, and 62.5 mg/ml. These solutions were stored at 4°C until further use.

Calculation of extraction yield

The extraction yield was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Yield (\%)} = (\text{mass of obtained material (dry extract residue)} / \text{initial mass of material}) \times 100.$$

Test organisms

The test organisms used in this study were the clinical isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* obtained from the diagnostic laboratory of the University of Abuja Teaching Hospital, Gwagwalada, Abuja, Nigeria. These bacteria were authenticated based on their culture characteristics, morphology, and biochemical tests following the method described in [15].

Antibacterial assay (diameter of inhibition zone, DIZ)

The agar-well diffusion method, as described in [14], was used to determine the growth inhibition effect of *D. cinerea* extracts on the test organisms. Mueller-Hinton agar was prepared as described above and 20 ml of it was aseptically poured into sterile Petri dishes. After solidification and drying, the agar was uniformly inoculated with a suspension of the test organism using a sterile glass hockey stick and left undisturbed for 30 min.

Four wells were bored into the agar using a sterile 6 mm diameter cork-borer, ensuring adequate separation to avoid overlapping zones of inhibition (at least 15 mm from the edge of the plate and 25 mm between wells). Three drops of *D. cinerea* stem bark extract at various concentrations (500, 250, 125, and 62.5 mg/ml) were added to the designated wells using

a Pasteur pipette. The inoculated plates were then incubated at 37°C for 18 h. Each concentration was tested in duplicate.

After incubation, zone diameters of inhibition were measured to the nearest millimeter using a graduated meter. According to [14], a zone of inhibition measuring at least 5 mm is considered indicative of antibacterial activity. Gram-positive bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*) were tested separately from the gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*). Ciprofloxacin (10 mg/ml) served as a positive control for all bacteria tested, while DMSO was used as a negative control.

Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC)

The method published in [16], with modifications as described in [17], was employed to measure the MIC using the broth dilution technique. The plant extract was prepared at a stock concentration of 500 mg/ml in sterile distilled water and serially diluted two-fold to working concentrations ranging from 500 mg/ml to 62.5 mg/ml in nutrient broth. Each concentration was inoculated with 0.2 ml of the test organism suspension. After incubation for 18 h at 37°C, turbidity of the solution in the tubes was observed. The lowest concentration of the plant extract that showed no turbidity was recorded as MIC.

Minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC)

To determine the MBC [15], samples from the tubes resulting from the MIC test were subcultured onto antimicrobial-free agar using a sterile wire loop, following the method described in [16] and [17]. The plates were then incubated at 37°C for 18 h. The lowest concentration of the extract that showed no bacterial growth on the agar plate was recorded as MBC.

Thin layer chromatography (TLC)

TLC was used to separate the compounds present in methanolic and ethanolic extracts. The TLC plates used were aluminum-backed silica gel 60 F254 (2.5×7.5 cm).

The spots were visualized by exposing the TLC plates to UV light at wavelengths of 254 and 366 nm, followed by exposure to iodine vapor [18].

Column Chromatography of *D. cinerea* Methanolic Extract

All solvents were redistilled to ensure analytical grade purity. The column was prepared using 45 g of silica gel (Hawach Scientific) (mesh size 300–400 µm) using the dry packing method. Five grams of the solid residue from the extract were pre-adsorbed onto silica gel and then loaded onto the column. An additional layer of silica gel was added to the top of the column before the addition of the solvent.

Separation was performed using a series of 100 ml eluents with increasing polarity. It was started with 100% hexane, then switched to hexane/ethyl acetate 9:1, 4:1, and 1:1, followed by ethyl acetate/hexane 7:3 and 4:1, and finally by 100% ethyl acetate.

A total of ten 30 ml fractions were collected in 50 ml beakers. After five days of air exposure, the solvents evaporated, yielding pale-yellow oily crystals and pale-yellow oils.

GC-MS

Components of the non-polar fraction of the methanolic extract of *D. cinerea* were analyzed by GC-MS. GC-MS analysis was conducted at the National Research Institute for Chemical Technology (NARICT) in Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria, using a SHIMADZU GCMS-QP 2010 Plus Instrument.

The GC-MS operational parameters were as follows: column oven temperature, 80°C; injection temperature, 250°C; injection mode, split; pressure, 108.0 kPa; total flow, 6.2 ml/min; column flow, 1.58 ml/min; linear velocity, 46.3 cm/s; and purge flow, 3.0 ml/min. The stationary phase used for GC was 5% diphenyl–95% dimethylpolysiloxane. The separated compounds were identified based on their mass spectra using a standard MS spectral library integrated with the GC-MS instrument and the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Mass Spectra Database.

Table 1. Physical characteristics of the dry residues of *D. cinerea* extracts

Plant part	Solvent	Weight, g	Yield, %	Color	Texture
Stem bark	Water	12.0	8.0	Dark brown	Gummy
	Ethanol	13.6	9.1	Light brown	Gummy
	Methanol	13.0	8.6	Light brown	Gummy

RESULTS

Physical characteristics of the dry residues of *D. cinerea* extracts

The physical characteristics of the dry residues of the aqueous, ethanolic, and methanolic extracts of *D. cinerea* stem bark are summarized in Table 1. These characteristics include the weight of the dry residue (g), percentage yield, color, and texture/feel.

Phytochemical Screening

Phytochemical screening of *D. cinerea* stem bark extracts revealed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, phlobatannins, and reducing sugars in all extracts (aqueous, ethanolic, and methanolic) (Table 2). Sterols, tannins, flavonoids, anthraquinones, and balsams were

absent in the aqueous extract, whereas glycosides were present only in the aqueous extract. Terpenoids were absent in all extracts.

Antibacterial assay

The diameters of the inhibition zones for the test organisms at different concentrations of the *D. cinerea* stem bark extracts are presented in Table 3. Low and high concentrations of aqueous, ethanolic, and methanolic extracts of *D. cinerea* stem bark exhibited antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. In the case of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, the aqueous extracts did not inhibit bacterial growth, whereas both the methanolic and ethanolic extracts showed antibacterial activity at all the concentrations tested.

Table 2. Phytochemical screening of *D. cinerea* stem bark extracts

Phytochemicals	Aqueous extract	Ethanolic extract	Methanolic extract
Sterols	-	+	+
Alkaloids	+	+	+
Tannins	-	+	+
Glycosides	+	-	-
Saponins	+	+	+
Flavonoids	-	+	+
Phlobatanins	+	+	+
Terpenoids	-	-	-
Reducing sugars	+	+	+
Anthraquinones	-	+	+
Balsams	-	+	+

Key: (+) – present, (-) – absent.

Table 3. Diameter of the inhibition zones (DIZ)

Test organism	Extraction solvent	DIZ (mm) at different concentrations of <i>D. cinerea</i> extracts (mg/ml)				
		62.5 mg/ml	125 mg/ml	250 mg/ml	500 mg/ml	Ciprofloxacin, 10 mg/ml
<i>D. cinerea</i> extracts						
	<i>S. aureus</i>					
<i>E. coli</i>						
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>						

No inhibition – no inhibition of bacterial growth

Determination of MIC of *D. cinerea* stem bark extracts

The MIC of *D. cinerea* stem bark extracts are listed in Table 4. Our results demonstrate that the growth of *E. coli* and *S. aureus* was inhibited by both ethanolic and methanolic extracts. At the same time, it was necessary to use the extracts at twice the concentration to inhibit *S. aureus* growth compared with the inhibition of *E. coli* growth.

Determination of the MBC of *D. cinerea* stem bark extracts

We investigated the bactericidal action of *D. cinerea* stem bark extracts at different concentrations on the growth of *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Table 5). The lowest concentration of *D. cinerea* extract that prevented bacterial growth on the nutrient agar plates corresponded to the MBC of this extract against the test organisms. Our results

showed that both ethanolic and methanolic extracts at a concentration of 500 mg/ml were bactericidal against *E. coli*.

TLC analysis of *D. cinerea* stem bark extracts

The compounds from the methanolic and ethanolic extracts of *D. cinerea* were separated by TLC using different ethyl acetate – hexanes mixtures as the eluents. The results showed that the best separation (five spots) was achieved with the ethyl acetate – hexanes 40:60 mixture, while the worst separation (two spots) was achieved with the ethyl acetate – hexanes 20:80 mixture (Table 6).

Column Chromatography Purification of *D. cinerea* stem bark methanolic extract

Components of the methanolic extract of *D. cinerea* stem bark were separated by column chromatography (Table 7).

Table 4. MIC of *D. cinerea* stem bark extracts

Bacterial Isolates	Extraction Solvent	Concentrations of extracts, mg/ml			
		62.5	125	250	500
<i>S. aureus</i>	Water	-	-	-	-
	Ethanol	-	-	-	MIC
	Methanol	-	-	-	MIC
<i>E. coli</i>	Water	-	-	-	-
	Ethanol	-	-	MIC	Inhibition observed
	Methanol	-	-	MIC	Inhibition observed
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Water	-	-	-	-
	Ethanol	-	-	-	-
	Methanol	-	-	-	-

(-) – no inhibition observed.

Table 5. MBC of *D. cinerea* stem bark extracts

Bacterial Isolates	Extraction Solvent	Concentrations of extracts, mg/ml			
		62.5	125	250	500
<i>S. aureus</i>	Water	-	-	-	-
	Ethanol	-	-	-	-
	Methanol	-	-	-	-
<i>E. coli</i>	Water	-	-	-	-
	Ethanol	-	-	-	MBC
	Methanol	-	-	-	MBC
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Water	-	-	-	-
	Ethanol	-	-	-	-
	Methanol	-	-	-	-

(-) – no suppression of bacterial growth observed.

Table 6. TLC analysis of the methanolic and ethanolic extracts of *D. cinerea*

TLC plate	Eluent ethyl acetate : hexanes	Ethanolic extract No. of spots on TLC	Methanolic extract No. of spots on TLC
1	0:100	4	3
2	20:80	2	2
3	40:60	5	5
4	100:0	4	3

Table 7. Elution pattern of *D. cinerea* stem bark methanolic extract

Hexane (%)	Ethyl acetate (%)	Samples collected
100	0	1
90	10	2 & 3
80	20	4
50	50	5 & 6
40	60	7
30	70	8
20	80	9
0	100	10

GC-MS analysis of the non-polar fraction of the methanolic stem bark extract of *D. cinerea*

Components of the non-polar fraction of the methanolic extract of *D. cinerea* were analyzed by GC-MS (Fig. 1, Table 8).

DISCUSSION

The physical properties of *D. cinerea* stem bark extracts obtained using different solvents indicate that ethanol extraction produces the highest final dry weight of extract – 13.6 g (9.1% yield) followed by methanol extraction – 13.0 g (8.6% yield), while the aqueous extraction produced the lowest final dry weight of 12.0 g (8.0% yield). The aqueous extract dry residue has a dark brown color and gummy texture, whereas the residues of the ethanolic and methanolic extracts both have a light brown color and gummy texture.

Phytochemical analysis of *D. cinerea* bark extracts revealed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, phlobatannins, and reducing sugars in all extracts (aqueous, ethanolic, and methanolic). However, sterols, tannins, flavonoids, anthraquinones, and balsams were absent in the aqueous extract, whereas glycosides were only detected in the aqueous extract. No terpenoids were detected in any of the extracts. Our findings are consistent with those published by Neondo et al. [19].

Flavonoids have been shown to affect membrane permeability, inhibit membrane-bound enzymes such as ATPase and phospholipase, and may contribute to the antioxidative properties of *D. cinerea* [20]. Our results showed that the bark contains saponins, which are known for their anti-inflammatory and immunostimulatory properties [21]. Tannins, which are effective in treating inflamed or ulcerated tissues, have notable anticancer and cancer-preventive activity [22, 23]. Alkaloids, also identified in *D. cinerea* extracts, are known for their medicinal properties and cytotoxicity [19]. The effectiveness of *D. cinerea* extracts against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria may be attributed to their alkaloid content, as these compounds have diverse antibacterial mechanisms of action, including binding to double-stranded DNA [24, 25].

The presence of phenolic compounds in *D. cinerea* extracts likely contributes to their antioxidative properties [26], thereby enhancing the potential of this plant in herbal medicine. Phenolic compounds are also beneficial in the preparation of antimicrobial agents. Some of them, such as Dettol and cresol, are used as disinfectants.

The aqueous extract did not contain sterols, tannins, flavonoids, anthraquinones, or balsams, indicating that water is unsuitable for the extraction of these compounds from *D. cinerea* bark.

As shown in Table 3, all *D. cinerea* stem bark extracts (aqueous, ethanolic, and methanolic) showed antibacterial activity against both *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* at all studied concentrations. According to the diameters of the inhibition zone, the order of inhibition activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* was aqueous extract < methanolic extract < ethanolic extract, while for *Escherichia coli*, it was aqueous extract < ethanolic extract < methanolic extract. In the case of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, the aqueous extract did not show antibacterial effects at any concentration, whereas the methanolic extract showed the highest activity, followed by the ethanolic extract, at all studied concentrations.

In general, higher concentrations of extracts were correlated with increased antibacterial activity across all solvents and test organisms. Among the three different extracts, the ethanolic and methanolic extracts provided larger inhibition zones than the aqueous extract, which could be attributed to the incomplete extraction of antibacterial compounds by water. These findings are consistent with those reported by Neondo et al. [19]. All organisms, including *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, were sensitive to methanolic and ethanolic extracts of *D. cinerea*. The aqueous extract was active against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, whereas *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was not sensitive to it.

Our results indicate that aqueous extracts of *D. cinerea* bark did not inhibit the growth of *S. aureus* or *E. coli* at any of the concentrations studied (Table 4). However, *S. aureus* did not grow at the highest concentrations (500 mg/ml) of either the ethanolic

or methanolic extracts (corresponding to the MIC), although growth was observed at lower extract concentrations – 250, 125, and 62.5 mg/ml. No growth of *E. coli* was recorded in the ethanolic and methanolic extracts at higher concentrations of 500 and 250 mg/ml (indicating MIC at 250 mg/ml), whereas growth of these bacteria was observed at lower concentrations of these extracts. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* exhibited growth when exposed to all extracts at all the studied concentrations. Inhibition of microbial growth under specific conditions can demonstrate the therapeutic efficacy of antimicrobial agents. Any slight modification of antibiotic molecules, which may be difficult to detect by physicochemical methods, is reflected in reduced antimicrobial activity. Thus, microbial assays are essential to identify potential reductions in antibiotic potency.

Our results showed that the growth of *S. aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was not suppressed by any of the extracts (Table 5). However, the growth of *E. coli* was suppressed by ethanolic and methanolic extracts at 500 mg/ml (MBC). This suggests that both the ethanolic and methanolic extracts of *D. cinerea* bark exhibited stronger activity against *E. coli*. These findings are consistent with the results obtained for the extracts of four other plant species published in [27].

The components of the methanolic *D. cinerea* stem bark extract were separated by column chromatography. Evaporation of non-polar fraction after the column chromatography produced a yellow viscous oil, which was analyzed using GC-MS. Eleven components of this

Fig. 1. Gas chromatogram of the non-polar fraction of the methanolic stem bark extract of *D. cinerea*.

Table 8. Components of the volatile oils of *D. cinerea* stem bark based on GC-MS analysis of the non-polar fraction of the methanolic extract

GC Peak, N	Name	RT ^a , min	Yield, %	(M ⁺) ^b Base peak mass	Structural formula
1	Dodecanoic acid, methyl ester	13.2	0.6	(214) 74	
2	Dodecanoic acid	14.4	2.17	(200) 41	
3	Tetradecanoic acid, methyl ester	15.9	0.92	(242) 74	
4	Tetradecanoic acid	17.0	2.77	(228) 43	
5	Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester	19.3	3.83	(270) 74	
6	Hexadecanoic acid	21.2	16.58	(256) 43	
7	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester	22.5	18.94	(294) 67	
8	Octadecanoic acid, methyl ester	22.8	2.63	(298) 74	
9	2-Methyl-Z, Z-3,13-octadecadienol	23.9	40.32	(280) 55	
10	n-Octadecanoic acid	24.1	9.09	(284) 43	
11	No match found	26.9	1.21	(265) 55	
12	No match found	27.6	0.48	(279) 57	
13	Tetracosanoic acid, methyl ester	29.1	0.46	(382) 74	

^aRT – retention time, min; ^b(M⁺) – Molecular ion mass (Daltons), Base peak mass (Daltons)

yellow oil were identified based on their mass spectra: four saturated fatty acids, five saturated fatty acid methyl esters, one unsaturated fatty acid methyl ester, and one unsaturated alcohol.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study agree with our hypothesis, demonstrating that *D. cinerea* stem bark extracts contain a wide range of bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, terpenoids, and phenolic acids, which explains the diverse biological activities of these extracts. Column chromatography and GC-MS analysis successfully identified and characterized some of these compounds. We achieved our objectives by elucidating the phytochemical composition of *D. cinerea* extracts and demonstrating that *D. cinerea* is a potential source

of novel bioactive compounds for pharmaceutical and medicinal applications.

We achieved our objectives by elucidating the phytochemical composition of *D. cinerea* extracts and demonstrating that they are a potential source of novel bioactive compounds for pharmaceutical and medicinal applications.

Our findings show that *D. cinerea* extracts require further investigation for their potential therapeutic benefits.

Several tannin-rich plants exhibit antimicrobial activities against various microorganisms. In this study, we investigated the phytochemical composition and antimicrobial activity of *D. cinerea* stem bark extracts. We observed the presence of tannins, alkaloids, flavonoids, reducing sugars, anthraquinones, balsams, saponins, sterols, and glycosides in these extracts, although

terpenoids were absent. All tested microorganisms, gram-positive (*S. aureus*) and gram-negative (*E. coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) bacteria, were susceptible to the extracts, with varying sensitivities depending on the concentration of the extracts. Tannins, known for their ability to disrupt bacterial cell walls and membranes [26], likely contribute to the observed antimicrobial effects.

D. cinerea stem bark extracts showed significant activity against both gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and gram-negative (*Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas*) bacteria. When comparing the extracts, it should be mentioned that ethanolic and methanolic extracts exhibited higher antimicrobial activity than aqueous extracts. Further studies are required to determine the antifungal activity of this plant.

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